

SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE BY DESIGN: ADDRESSING SOCIAL ASPECTS OF CIRCULARITY IN THE ANALYST PROJECT

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Extended Abstract

Plastic pollution has become a systemic threat to ecosystems, human health and climate objectives, prompting the European Union (EU) to strengthen action across the plastics value chain (European Commission, 2023). Global plastic production reached about 370 Mt in 2020, with Europe representing a significant share of demand and manufacturing (PlasticsEurope, 2022). Beyond material volumes, the chemical complexity of plastics is increasingly central: polymers are formulated with additives (e.g., plasticisers, stabilisers, flame retardants) that may migrate or be released during use, recycling and disposal. This raises worry about “substances of concern” and creates constraints for safe circularity (Hahladakis et al., 2018).

Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) is one of the most widely produced plastics worldwide that exemplifies these challenges. Although valued for durability and chemical resistance, PVC’s additive content and end-of-life (EoL) management can limit safe recycling and complicate risk control (European Commission, 2022). In response, EU initiatives such as the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan and the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability promote a transition towards safer material cycles, reinforced by REACH and the Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) approach (EU, 2006; European Commission, 2019, 2020a, 2020b, 2021, 2022a; JRC, 2022).

SSbD is a key pillar of the European Chemicals Strategy (EC, 2020) aiming to minimise human and environmental exposure to hazardous substances and other stressors, while fostering their substitution with safer and more sustainable options (e.g., bio-based chemicals), advanced materials, and improved alternatives. To support implementation, the Joint Research Centre (JRC) developed a framework to define SSbD criteria for chemicals and materials, including a structured description of the aspects that should be addressed (Caldeira et al., 2022), and revised it in December 2025 (Garmendia Aguirre et al., 2025). SSbD is grounded in a holistic Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) perspective, which evaluates products and/or services across their full life cycle (from raw material extraction to end-of-life management) consistent with ISO 14040/44:2021. Within the LCT approaches, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) quantifies environmental impacts; Life Cycle Costing (LCC) examines costs incurred over the life cycle; and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) addresses social and socio-economic aspects associated with the life cycle of products. These approaches can be integrated through Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA), which combines the environmental, economic, and social dimensions of sustainability. More recently, the EU Horizon 2020 ORIENTING project proposed an operational

methodology to facilitate this integrated assessment, explicitly incorporating additional considerations such as criticality.

A key barrier to developing and implementing SSbD is the fragmentation of assessment practices. Risk assessment typically focuses on hazard and exposure, while LCT approaches address environmental burdens and socio-economic aspects using different boundaries and metrics. In circular value chains, such fragmentation can enable burden shifting (e.g., higher recycling rates accompanied by increased worker exposure or consumer risks). The EU has also highlighted data gaps on hazardous additives and the need for updated polymer safety criteria (European Commission, 2022). Decision-relevant tools that integrate evidence across health, environmental, social and economic dimensions are therefore required to operationalise SSbD and guide substitution and innovation choices. PVC is a particularly demanding test case because EoL options depend on additive content, traceability, and the coexistence of legacy and modern formulations. Circularity strategies must, therefore, be assessed not only for material and energy recovery, but also for exposure control, socio-economic feasibility and societal acceptability. Within this context, the project ANALYST, funded by Horizon Europe, aims to develop an integrated approach to support safer and more sustainable PVC value chains and to strengthen consumer confidence. The integrated approach is being developed to implement the SSbD framework and incorporates the latest advanced research conducted by the ORIENTING project to assess circularity aspects across the entire life cycle.

In particular, this study aims to highlight how circularity is addressed in ANALYST project, paying attention to the social assessment step of the SSbD framework.

The SSbD structure is articulated in five steps: Step 1 addresses intrinsic hazard; Steps 2–3 combine hazard and exposure information to assess risks during production/processing (including occupational settings across life-cycle stages, potentially including EoL operations) and during final application (consumer and environmental exposure), respectively; Step 4 evaluates environmental sustainability through LCA; and Step 5, not mandatory, expands to socio-economic sustainability, covering social fairness and competitiveness.

SSbD is an iterative and context-adaptive assessment rather than strictly sequential, strengthening the role of scoping and engagement with relevant life-cycle actors. Therefore, case-by-case could be modelled and verified according to the understudy system and the different Technological Readiness Levels (TRLs) reached. ANALYST project finalised its integrated approach through three complementary components. 1) ANALYST-T-PACK supports training and structured academia–industry collaboration, enabling real-world validation, knowledge transfer and consolidation of best practices along the PVC value chain. 2) ANALYST-BOX provides the methodological backbone by integrating evidence across health/safety, environmental, social and economic dimensions in line with the European SSbD framework. 3) ANALYST-DIGI implements this logic in a digital decision-support environment, enabling transparent comparison of alternatives, structured reporting, and explicit handling of uncertainty; data-science methods (including natural language processing) support evidence extraction and help address missing data.

Methodologically, ANALYST-BOX is anchored in the SSbD framework (i.e., the five steps mentioned above), which combines (i) a (re)design stage—covering molecular, process and product design choices—and (ii) a life-cycle-based assessment stage, preceded by structured scoping to define function, scenarios, system boundaries and innovation maturity. The assessment follows a tiered logic aligned with technology readiness: screening-level evaluations are prioritised in early phases, while progressively more quantitative and comprehensive analyses become feasible at higher TRLs. Integration in ANALYST-BOX is operationalised through an

action-oriented dimension scoring (1–3) and a transparent aggregation workflow using an Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)-based Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA). This is complemented by non-compensatory decision rules (minimum requirements per dimension to prevent unacceptable trade-offs) and explicit signalling of uncertainty and evidence reliability, particularly relevant for early-stage innovations. Importantly, circularity is treated as a cross-cutting domain rather than a standalone recycling metric: EoL strategies are evaluated for implications on additive recirculation and exposure, process emissions and energy demand, working conditions in waste and recycling operations, and economic feasibility. This enables the selection of circular strategies that are compatible with SSbD principles.

The project's contribution is a structured, operational pathway to implement SSbD in PVC value chains, including practical guidance oriented to recycling-related decision-making under industrial performance constraints. By combining ANALYST-BOX and ANALYST-DIGI, the project supports the evaluation of closed-loop and open-loop recycling options and clarifies the conditions under which circularity targets can be pursued without compromising safety, product functionality or broader sustainability requirements.

A key conceptual advance concerns how circularity is interpreted within SSbD: circularity is not treated as a purely technical outcome (e.g., higher recovery rates), but as an outcome that must be demonstrably safe, socially acceptable and governance-compliant. S-LCA and just transition perspectives indicate that EoL assessments should consider occupational health and safety, job quality and labour rights, inclusion of informal waste workers where relevant, impacts on local communities and social acceptability of facilities, consumer trust and transparency, and governance mechanisms such as grievance systems and social auditing (UNEP, 2020; ILO, 2023; ISO, 2024; Cook et al., 2024). This broader lens is critical because EoL stages can concentrate exposure and vulnerability and because circular value chains may redistribute risks and benefits across actor groups.

At the same time, EoL is often oversimplified in existing assessments: even when included in system boundaries, the actors implementing circular practices (such as workers in sorting and recycling facilities and informal recycling networks) are frequently omitted, reducing policy relevance and weakening the link to circular economy mechanisms (Alvarez & Ligart, 2021). The challenge is amplified for emerging technologies, where social data are sparse, and uncertainty is high, making stakeholder mapping and indicator selection particularly complex (Muazu et al., 2024). In ANALYST, socio-economic assessment is therefore designed to remain decision-relevant across maturity levels by clarifying which social perspectives become critical under different TRLs and market contexts, especially for consumer-facing applications, where user practices and acceptance can influence collection, sorting, contamination rates and ultimately the feasibility of recycling routes.

In conclusion, ANALYST project provides a decision-ready framework that aligns circularity with safety and sustainability requirements for PVC innovations and alternatives. Its main contributions include: (i) transparent, threshold-based integration that limits burden shifting; (ii) explicit and testable value judgments through AHP-based weighting and sensitivity analysis; and (iii) a digital decision-support tool enabling scalable application and consistent reporting, including uncertainty. Across the PVC case studies, the approach is expected to identify hotspots related to additive risks, compare EoL pathways that maximise material recovery while controlling exposure and environmental impacts, and operationalise socially grounded indicators that capture worker- and community-level implications of circular practices. For research, the work advances practical integration of heterogeneous assessment traditions into a coherent SSbD decision framework. For industry, it provides implementable guidance for redesigning PVC products and

processes for safe circularity, including decision rules, data needs and transparent documentation of uncertainty. For policy, it supports targeted data generation and may inform consistent implementation of EU sustainability strategies and future REACH-related discussions (EU, 2006; European Commission, 2022a).

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